

Sputter coating of lithium metal electrodes with lithiophilic metals for homogeneous and reversible lithium electrodeposition and electrodisolution

Marian Cristian Stan^{a,*}, Jens Becking^a, Aleksei Kolesnikov^a, Björn Wankmiller^b, Joop Enno Frerichs^b, Michael Ryan Hansen^b, Peter Bieker^{a,b}, Martin Kolek^a, Martin Winter^{a,c,*}

^aMEET Battery Research Center, University of Münster, Corrensstrasse 46, 48149 Münster, Germany

^bInstitute of Physical Chemistry, University of Münster, Corrensstrasse 28-30, 48149 Münster, Germany

^cHelmholtz Institute Münster (HI MS), IEK-12, Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH, Corrensstrasse 46, 48149 Münster, Germany

Inhomogeneous lithium (Li) deposition leads to the formation of dendrites and “dead” Li, which is a limiting factor for the commercial success of Li metal batteries (LMBs). Herein, the sputter coating of Li metal electrodes by the sputter deposition method with lithiophilic metals, such as gold (Au) or zinc (Zn), was used in order to improve the electrochemical performance of Li metal electrodes. The structural characterization of such electrodes after the sputter deposition process indicated the presence of the corresponding Li-intermetallic phase ($\text{Li}_{15}\text{Au}_4$, LiZn) at the surface of the Li metal electrodes. Morphological investigations showed that the Li-intermetallic phases were able to steer the electrodeposition of Li beneath the Li-intermetallic coating, resulting in homogeneous dispersion of the Li deposits. The electrochemical measurements in symmetrical $\text{Li}|\text{Li}$ cells also indicated reduced overvoltages. Up to a cycled capacity of 0.2825 mAh/cm^2 , these electrodes showed stable overvoltage for the lithium electrodisolution and electrodeposition process in comparison to pristine Li metal electrodes. Furthermore, in $\text{S8}|\text{Li}$ cells, the overpotentials of sputter coated Li metal electrodes (Au@Li , Zn@Li) during operation are highly reduced compared to pristine Li metal electrodes. Thus, the results presented here, indicate that sputter coating of Li metal electrodes represents a promising approach to improve the performance of high energy LMBs through engineering of the Li metal interphase.

Introduction

The re-investigation of lithium (Li) metal as anode material for lithium secondary (rechargeable) batteries, such as in high energy density lithium metal batteries (LMBs) with sulfur (S_8), oxygen (O_2) or layered transition metal oxide cathodes in liquid electrolytes, is still being challenged by its intrinsic characteristic of inhomogeneous re-deposition during cycling, resulting in the formation of high surface area lithium (HSAL), including the growth of lithium dendrites [1–6]. Usually, the term HSAL is

interchangeable with microstructural lithium, mentioned in other publications [7,8], and refers here to a lithium deposit morphology (e.g. needle-, moss- and whisker-like structures) that differs from the bulk Li metal foil. With increasing cycle number, the continuous Li electrodeposition (“plating”) and electrodisolution (“stripping”) with poor Coulombic efficiency results also in isolation of the electroactive material and formation of electrochemically inactive Li, so-called “dead” Li, which remains chemically highly reactive. Such detrimental behavior leads to an accumulation of the isolated “dead” Li deposits, low cycling performance and continuous electrolyte consumption resulting in low performance and increased safety concerns. Various

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: Stan, M.C. (marian.stan@uni-muenster.de), Winter, M. (martin.winter@uni-muenster.de).

approaches are actively considered to avoid and/or minimize the effect of such challenges prior to commercialization of LMBs [9–11].

In principle, these challenges are related to the formation of HSAL, which is strongly dependent on the chemical and electrochemical behavior of metallic Li prior and during the reduction process. Consequently, the strategies reported in literature [5,10,12] focus mainly on fundamental approaches, which: (i) improve the compatibility of the Li metal electrodes towards reactive species, such as electrolyte components using protective layers; (ii) direct the flux of Li-ions towards an homogeneous and HSAL-free electrodeposition; (iii) improve the overall electrochemical performance, e.g. current density distribution by Li metal electrode morphology design; and (iv) improve the interphase/interface properties by surface engineering of Li metal electrode. Often, interface design is the strategy of choice for multiple electrolyte systems in combination with Li metal electrodes. Therefore, the tailoring of the Li metal electrode's surface should be adapted to each system and accordingly to the coating properties and its focused environment. For example, engineered interphases, fabricated from a solvent-based chemical reaction using either organic compounds [13,14], inorganic salts [15–18], glasses or carbons (C) [19] to form a kind of solid electrolyte interphase (SEI [20–23]), are intentionally created to match with selected purposes and are therefore called artificial [24,25]. Some of these engineering methods are using *ex situ* (preparation of the protection layer prior to cell assembly [26]) or *in situ* (aging of Li metal electrode in a solution [27]) approaches. Solvent-free methods, which are able to modify the surface of the Li metal electrodes, usually use mechanical [28–31] and/or physical methods (e.g. sputter deposition) to generate electrodes with better electrochemical performance [32].

Using magnetron sputtering, Zhang et al. [33] prepared a C coating on Li metal electrodes that prevented the formation of Li dendrites when cycled in a carbonate-based electrolyte. The cells assembled with Li metal electrodes where an excessive thickness of the C coating (110 nm) was used, resulted in reduced cell performance with increased cell impedance due to the reduced Li-ions transfer. Other efforts, as presented by Chen et al. [34] and Song et al. [35], focused mainly on the modification of copper (Cu) substrates by the addition of lithiophilic layers, such as gold (Au) and zinc (Zn), respectively. These layers have a high affinity for Li-ion uptake thus, are able to reduce both the interfacial resistance and the polarization overvoltage of the lithium electrodeposition. However, in such approaches, the engineered Cu substrates/current collectors need to be further loaded with Li (mostly via an electrochemical process) prior assembly in full-cells (especially when combined with electrode materials that do not contain any electrochemically active Li-ions, such as in $S_8||Li$ batteries).

For example, Dahn and co-workers [36], using a high throughput combinatorial 64-cell array, investigated the coating thickness effect of a Zn-coated Cu foil on the efficiency of $Cu||Li$ cells using fluorinated carbonates as electrolytes. The preformation of a Li-intermetallic phase (LiZn) followed by the lithium electrodeposition significantly improved the Coulombic efficiency of the presented half-cells. Tang et al. [37] used direct coating of porous non-lithiophilic Cu on Li metal electrodes by

magnetron sputtering to stabilize the electrochemical performance of such electrodes and also to suppress the formation of Li dendrites. The Cu layer on Li metal electrodes ($Cu@Li$) could successfully decrease the initial interfacial resistance in $Cu@Li$ -symmetric-cells and provided superior electrochemical performance in $S_8||Li$ full-cells.

Regardless of the considered approaches [38–41], the use of the sputter deposition method for Li metal electrodes is still very scarce. Therefore, improved methods and materials are needed to achieve further improvements in electrochemical performance, especially when LMBs are focused to maximize energy values and cycling of Li metal electrodes with high capacities.

Herein, using the sputter deposition method, lithiophilic metals (able to form Li-intermetallic phases) such as Au or Zn were coated directly on the surface of the Li metal electrodes with the focus to control, guide, and homogenize the lithium electrodeposition and electrodisolution. Removal of the Li metal electrode's surface roughness by means of roll-pressing method [29] was carried out prior to sputter deposition process. The morphological and electrochemical investigations have pointed out that the newly formed interphase, mainly consisting of a defined LiM-intermetallic phase ($Li_{15}Au_4$, LiZn), is able to guide a homogeneous lithium electrodeposition and electrodisolution. This was due to a fast electron and Li-ion transfer that further smoothens the overvoltage shape [42] and reduces the hysteresis of the electrochemical processes. Furthermore, during the initial cycle the morphological changes of the Li metal electrodes coated with lithiophilic Au or with Zn, indicated a suppressed formation of pits and voids (i.e. homogeneous lithium electrodisolution). The fundamental behavior of such intermetallic phases was investigated in a “Li-free anode” configuration using $Cu||Li$ cells, where either lithiophilic Au or Zn were sputtered on the Cu substrate. Finally, electrochemical performance of such engineered Li metal electrodes was also assessed in full-cells using S_8 composite cathodes, where superior performance compared to the pristine Li metal electrodes baseline could be achieved. Based on the results presented here, the modification of the Li metal electrode's surface, using Li-intermetallic phases (e.g. with $Li_{15}Au_4$ or with LiZn), could enable uniform Li electrodeposition and thus demonstrate the practicality of such electrodes in rechargeable LMBs.

Material and methods

Li metal electrodes were prepared from battery grade Li foil (500 μm , Livent Corp.) by first roll-pressing [29] the Li foil on Cu substrate (50 μm , Schlenk AG) using a bench top calendaring machine HSAM-615H (Hohsen Corp., Japan) to a final thickness of 150 μm . These are further denoted as pristine Li metal electrodes. Disks with a diameter of 12 mm were punched out and sputtered with Au (45 mA, 260 s) or Zn (60 mA, 310 s) at $\approx 5 \times 10^{-3}$ mbar using a bench top sputter coater Q150T (Quorum Technologies Ltd.). The predetermined thickness of the metal coating (100 nm) was timed monitored by sputter coating *a priori* a silicon wafer (with Au or Zn) and measuring the coating thickness using a profilometer (DektakXT, Bruker). The Li metal electrodes sputter coated with lithiophilic Au or Zn will be referred to as $Au@Li$ or $Zn@Li$ metal electrodes, respectively, or by mention-

ing the Li-intermetallic phase ($\text{Li}_{15}\text{Au}_4$, LiZn) that forms at the surface of the Li metal electrodes.

Electrochemical characterization of the Li metal electrodes (pristine, Au@Li , Zn@Li) was carried out at 20 °C using a MACCOR battery cycler (MACCOR Series 4000). For that, Li-symmetric (Li||Li , Au@Li||Au@Li , Zn@Li||Zn@Li), Cu||Li-based (Cu||Li , Au@Cu||Li , Zn@Cu||Li) and S_8 ||Li-based (S_8 ||Li, S_8 || Au@Li and S_8 || Zn@Li) cells were assembled using either 2-electrode cells (CR2032) or 3-electrode cells [43] (Swagelok[®], in house design). For the cells using reference electrode, pristine Li metal (“as received”) was used. The separator assembly for the 2-electrode cells was composed of two Celgard 2500 layers backing 2 layers of a nonwoven polypropylene separator (FS2190, Freudenberg). For all S_8 ||Li-based cells, one layer of Celgard 2500 facing the counter electrode and 2 layers of the FS2190 separator were used instead. In all experiments, 1 M lithium bis(trifluoromethane)sulfonimide (LiTFSI) in a mixture of 1,3-dioxolane (DOL) and 1,2-dimethoxyethane (DME) 1:1 (v/v) was used as electrolyte. The electrolyte amount for 2-electrode cells was 60 μL , while for S_8 ||Li-based cells the amount of electrolyte was calculated based on the sulfur active material (electrolyte-to-sulfur ratio (E/S) = 10:1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{mgS}_8$) considering an average loading of ca. 2.5 mg/cm^2 . The S_8 ||Li-based cells were cycled galvanostatically at a C-rate of 0.1C (where 1C corresponds to 1675 mA/g) for the first 10 cycles followed by 0.2C for the rest of the cycling within the potential range of 1.5 V–3 V vs. Li|Li^+ . The potential of the counter electrode was recorded using the auxiliary inputs of the battery tester. Li-symmetric cells (Li||Li cells using either pristine or sputter coated Li metal electrodes) were cycled using the voltage limitations of –1.5 V for the electrodeposition and 1.5 V for electro-dissolution at various current densities. For electrochemical characterization, the cells were assembled under inert Ar-atmosphere in a glove box (MBraun).

Morphological investigation was carried out on a Carl Zeiss Auriga Modular Crossbeam scanning electron microscope (SEM). The electron source was a Schottky field emission gun with a Gemini column. Images were taken at 3 kV accelerating voltage using an in lens secondary electron detector. The lens opening was 30 μm and the working distance approx. 5 mm. The electron beam of the SEM did not induce any modifications of the surface topography during exposure. For these morphological investigations the cycled electrodes, were recovered from the cycled cells and washed with DME (Alfa Aesar) several times inside of a glove box. Structural composition of the sputter coated Li metal electrodes was investigated by means of X-Ray diffraction (XRD) on a D8 Advance diffractometer (Bruker) using Cu K- α radiation ($\lambda_{\text{Cu}} = 0.15418 \text{ nm}$) and equipped with a Lynx-Eye 1-dimensional Position Sensitive Detector (PSD). The patterns were recorded between 20 to 80 degree 2θ range using a step size of 0.02 degree and a time per step of 0.2 s. To carry out the measurements, the sputter coated Li metal electrodes were fixed on the sample holder (single crystal silicon) using a special tape that avoided the contact with air and moisture during the measurement ($\approx 10 \text{ min}$). No additional reflections from the sample holder or special tape were observed.

Operando ^7Li NMR measurements of Li||Li and Zn@Li||Zn@Li symmetric cells were performed using a cell configuration as described by Küpers et al. [44]. The pouch cells were assembled

inside a dry room (dew point was –55 °C) and where then activated by adding 200 μL of the electrolyte and sealed under reduced pressure prior the lithium electrodeposition that occurred by applying a current density of 0.5 mA/cm^2 for 8 h (measurement recorded every 30 min). The ^7Li NMR experiments were performed on a Bruker DSX spectrometer equipped with a widebore magnet operating at 200 MHz (4.7 T) using an in-house build broadband NMR probe, which allows for electric operation of the cell inside the NMR magnet. The ^7Li NMR spectra were referenced to 1 M LiCl in H_2O and the ^7Li resonance was set to 0 ppm. All experiments were performed at a resonance frequency of 77.8 MHz with a nutation frequency of 17.9 kHz. The recycle delay between transients was set to 2 s and every ^7Li NMR spectrum was acquired using 833 transients, leading to total time of ca. 30 min per spectrum. Spectral analyses and fitting of the data were achieved using the DmFit program [45]. It is worth mentioning that the skin depth of the excitation pulse is a function of known physical constants and can be readily calculated [46], which for Li metal equals 17.4 μm , i.e., the detected ^7Li NMR signals should reflect the amount of deposited lithium.

Results and discussion

Li-intermetallic phases were thoroughly investigated as possible candidates for anode active materials for lithium ion batteries (LIBs) mainly due to their promised higher capacity as compared to the state-of-the-art anode material, e.g. graphite [47–50]. However, upon continuous cycling, their poor mechanical performance, leading to particle pulverization, disregarded pure Li-intermetallic phases as active electrode materials, although composites including large amounts of carbon or nanoparticles showed an improved behavior [47]. Nevertheless, the Li-ion transport properties are highly enhanced in such Li-intermetallic phases, therefore a combination of such materials with Li metal electrodes could result in an improvement of the overall performance of such engineered electrodes.

Fig. 1 shows the structural composition of the Li metal electrodes after the sputter coating process with lithiophilic metals such as Au and Zn. These electrodes contained no Cu substrate. The XRD pattern of the Au@Li electrode reveals only the pres-

FIGURE 1

Comparison of the XRD patterns of the Li metal electrodes with a thickness of 150 μm and after sputter coating with Au (green) and Zn (blue).

ence of $\text{Li}_{15}\text{Au}_4$ -intermetallic phase (PDF No. 01-073-2900) and metallic Li reflections. In the case of the Zn@Li electrode, the corresponding pattern shows only the characteristic reflection for metallic Li and the LiZn -intermetallic phase (PDF No. 03-065-3016). In both cases, neither remaining metallic Au nor Zn were identified. Such results imply that the complete consumption of the sputtered metals by formation of the corresponding Li-intermetallic phase already occurred during the sputter deposition process (see Experimental Section for the corresponding sputter conditions). The formation of an intermetallic phase was also observed in the case of Au, when the discoloration of the golden Au coating present at the surface of the Li metal electrode slowly disappeared and turned – within minutes after the chamber was opened – into the dark-gray color of the $\text{Li}_{15}\text{Au}_4$ -intermetallic phase coating.

The formation of the $\text{Li}_{15}\text{Au}_4$ and LiZn intermetallic phases at the surface of the sputter coated Li metal electrodes indicate the lithiophilic character of both Au and Zn when brought in contact with metallic Li. It is assumed that once these intermetallic phases are formed at the surface of Li metal electrodes, they remain connected to the bulk lithium, and the de-lithiation reaction of $\text{Li}_{15}\text{Au}_4$ and LiZn intermetallic phases will not occur. To further investigate this aspect, Cu substrates were sputter-coated with lithiophilic Au or Zn layers, and the formation of the corresponding Li-intermetallic phases, in the electrochemical process involving Au@Cu||Li and Zn@Cu||Li cells, was followed. Fig. 2 shows a basic overview of the electrochemical activity of

Au@Cu and Zn@Cu electrodes with a thickness of the lithiophilic layer of 100 nm.

In Fig. 2a, the formation of Li-intermetallic phases can be followed in the current–potential curves recorded for Au@Cu||Li and Zn@Cu||Li cells in a potential range that was limited to 0.05 V vs. Li|Li^+ in order to avoid lithium electrodeposition. The formation of the LiZn -intermetallic phase occurs at ≈ 0.45 V vs. Li|Li^+ while the formation of $\text{Li}_{15}\text{Au}_4$ -intermetallic phases is observed to occur below 0.2 V vs. Li|Li^+ . In the investigated potential range, the cyclic voltammogram for the Cu||Li 3-electrode cell (orange color in Fig. 2a) did not show the presence of any redox process. During the release of Li-ions (anodic scan, oxidation process), current peaks at potentials ≈ 0.2 V vs. Li|Li^+ or higher were observed, depending on the nature of the Li-intermetallic phase. The redox processes during the 1st cycle were also reproducible during the 2nd cycle. In Fig. 2b the voltage profiles of the Au@Cu||Li and Zn@Cu||Li 2-electrode cells obtained during the 1st cycle using a current density of 0.25 mA/cm^2 and for a total capacity of 0.8475 mAh, are presented. The occurrence of the voltage plateaus was in accordance with the results presented in Fig. 2a. Since in these experiments the total amount of charge used was 0.8475 mAh and this overcomes the capacity needed only for the formation of the corresponding Li-intermetallic phase (0.1115 mAh for the formation of $\text{Li}_{15}\text{Au}_4$ and 0.1404 mAh for the formation of LiZn , respectively), also Li electrodeposition occurred. Furthermore, the resulting Coulombic efficiency (Fig. 2c) recorded from the

FIGURE 2

Comparison of (a) cyclic voltammograms of Au@Cu and Zn@Cu electrodes recorded with a scan rate of $50 \mu\text{V/s}$; (b) voltage profiles of Cu||Li , Au@Cu||Li , and Zn@Cu||Li cells during the initial cycle with cut-off parameters of -1.5 V and 1.5 V voltage or a total capacity of 0.8475 mAh; (c–d) Coulombic efficiency of Cu||Li , Au@Cu||Li , and Zn@Cu||Li cells with a voltage cut-off value of (c) 1.5 V and (d) 0.2 V and a current density of 0.25 mA/cm^2 for 1 h. In all experiments the electrolyte was 1 M LiTFSI in DME:DOL 1:1 (v/v).

2-electrode cells (Cu||Li, Au@Cu||Li, Zn@Cu||Li) during 100 cycles at a current density of 0.25 mA/cm^2 (applied for 1 hour or with voltage limitations of: -1.5 V for electrodeposition and 1.5 V for electrodis-solution process) showed deteriorating electrochemical performance. In fact, the amount of lithium used for the formation of the Li-intermetallic phase decreased and after only 15 cycles the electrochemical activity in these electrodes corresponding to the Li uptake and release from the Li-intermetallic phase vanished, leaving only the characteristic voltage profiles of the lithium electrodeposition and electrodis-solution reaction (Fig. S1). The results in Fig. 2d present the Coulombic efficiency recorded from similar cells with the upper voltage value limited at 0.2 V for the lithium electrodis-solution process. It was intended to reduce detrimental processes occurring at more positive voltages. These cells show indeed improved Coulombic efficiencies which imply an improved capacity retention, as compared to the cells where the upper voltage value was limited at 1.5 V (Fig. 2c, Li release from the Li-intermetallic phase occurred).

The morphological investigation of the Au@Cu and Zn@Cu electrodes before and after Li uptake of 0.8475 mAh was carried out and the results are presented in Fig. S2. In the case of the Au@Cu electrodes (Fig. S2a-b) the main morphological changes are represented by the formation of the HSAL and the disconnection of the $\text{Li}_{15}\text{Au}_4$ -intermetallic phase from Cu substrate driven by the growth of HSAL. A similar behavior was observed for the Zn@Cu electrodes after 0.8475 mAh Li uptake by the Zn lithiophilic layer to form the LiZn-intermetallic phase followed by

lithium electrodeposition (Fig. S2c-d). Previously, Yan and co-workers [51] explained that lithiophilic metals such as Au and Zn show no nucleation barriers for the lithium electrodeposition due to the solubility of these metals in Li. Furthermore, the results from Fig. S2b,d indicate that beyond the formation of the LiZn-intermetallic phase, the excess of lithium (i.e. lithium HSAL) is redirected towards the surface of the Cu substrate, i.e. the phase with no solubility in Li. Such observations clearly indicate that the $\text{Li}_{15}\text{Au}_4$ or LiZn interphases facilitate an efficient flux of Li-ions towards the Li-intermetallic|Cu-electrode interface, thus this approach was considered as a possible solution towards the prevention and formation of Li HSAL [51,52].

Fig. 3 shows the effect on the morphological evolution of the Li deposits within the 1st cycle of the pristine Li, Au@Li and Zn@Li electrodes. Upon cycling, the morphological changes occurring at the Li metal electrode have a huge impact on the further electrochemical performance of these electrodes and also on the overall performance of the LMBs. In Fig. 3a–c, the evolution of the surface morphology of the pristine Li metal electrodes reveals the formation of pits and voids as the Li is electrodis-solved. Such major morphological change occurred already when a total amount of charge equal to 0.8475 mAh was removed from the surface of the pristine Li metal electrode (Fig. 3b). The electrodeposition of the Li occurred with the formation of Li agglomerates (Figs. 3c and S3a). When Au@Li metal electrodes were used (pristine, Fig. 3d) neither the formation of pits and voids nor the breakdown of the intermetallic layer was observed during the first lithium electrodis-solution (Fig. 3e).

FIGURE 3

Morphology evolution of (a–c) Li metal electrodes, (d–f) Au@Li electrodes and (g–i) Zn@Li electrodes. The SEM images present (a,d,g) the pristine state of these electrodes, and electrodes (b,e,h) after the first electrodis-solution and (c,f,i) after first electrodeposition. Li-symmetric cells were cycled using a current density of 0.25 mA/cm^2 and a total amount of lithium transported corresponding to 0.8475 mAh . In all experiments the electrolyte was 1 M LiTFSI in DME:DOL 1:1 (v/v).

However, a homogeneous lithium electrodeposition (Fig. 3f) occurred without the formation of singular bulky Li deposits as shown in Fig. 3c. In this case, smaller Li deposits were formed between the cracks present in the $\text{Li}_{15}\text{Au}_4$ coating (Fig. S3b). The Li metal electrodes sputter coated with lithiophilic Zn (pristine, Fig. 3g), did not behave differently as the Au@Li electrodes, and neither these showed the formation of pits and voids (Fig. 3h) or the formation of HSAL during the lithium electrodeposition process (Fig. 3i).

SEM cross-section investigations of the Zn@Li metal electrodes, after an incremental amount of electrodeposited Li are provided in Fig. 4. Compared with the pristine electrodes, after the deposition of a low amount of Li (0.2825 mAh, Fig. 4b), it is observed that the LiZn-intermetallic layer redirects the lithium electrodeposition mainly below the LiZn-intermetallic layer. This indicates that the LiZn-intermetallic layer is able to alleviate the formation of HSAL. As the Li amount increased to 0.8475 mAh, the formation of Li deposits on the surface of the Zn@Li metal electrode was observed (Fig. 4c). These observations together with the observations made in Fig. 3 are summarized schematically in Fig. 4d-e, and further support that the LiZn-intermetallic phases homogenizes and controls the flux of Li-ion at the surface of the Li metal electrode during the lithium electrodisolution and electrodeposition process. Similarly to the morphological changes observed for the Zn@Cu electrodes upon the uptake of Li, in the present case, the presence of the Li-intermetallic phase at the surface of Li metal electrodes will act more as a solid electrolyte that facilitates the conduction of Li-ions towards the interface Li-intermetallic|Li metal, thus facilitating an effective transport of Li-ions for lithium electrodeposition. These results also indicate that the intermetallic phases remain in contact with the excess of bulk metallic Li, thus pre-

venting the release of Li from the $\text{Li}_{15}\text{Au}_4$ and LiZn intermetallic phases.

Engineering the interphase of the Li metal electrode, combined with the development of non-destructive *operando* characterization methods, brings valuable knowledge in further understanding the behavior of such electrodes. Non-destructive methods such as *operando* ^7Li NMR were successfully used to identify the formation of microstructural Li (i.e. Li dendrites, also referred here to HSAL) upon cycling in Li||Li symmetrical cells with various electrolytes [8,44]. Here, *operando* ^7Li NMR measurements were used to investigate further the role of the LiZn intermetallic phases during the lithium electrodeposition reaction, with special focus on the ability of the intermetallic phase to control (redirect) the electrodeposition of metallic Li, i.e. effective suppression of HSAL. Fig. 5 summarizes the formation of HSAL for the Li metal electrode sputter coated with lithiophilic Zn layer and the results are compared with the pristine Li metal electrode.

Fig. 5 presents the results obtained from successive ^7Li NMR measurements within an interval of 60 min during electrodeposition with a current density of 0.5 mA/cm^2 . The data shown are based on the ratio between the integrals for the ^7Li metal signal (246 ppm, Li bulk) and the emerging ^7Li signal centered ≈ 269 ppm for pristine Li and 267 ppm for Zn@Li, corresponding to Li HSAL (see Fig. S4a,b). The data in Fig. 5 clearly demonstrates the difference between the behavior of the two electrodes with less Li deposits (Li HSAL) forming at the Zn@Li metal electrode as compared to the pristine Li metal electrode when the same amount of charge has been passed. The difference is noticeable from the slope as indicated by the extrapolated lines between the data points, where the increase of the ^7Li HSAL signal (representative for the amount of formed

FIGURE 4

SEM cross-section images of the Zn@Li electrodes (a) pristine, (b) after the electrodeposition of 0.2825 mAh and (c) after the electrodeposition of 0.8475 mAh. The symmetric-cells (a–c) were cycled using a current density of 0.25 mA/cm^2 . Schematic representation of the morphological changes occurring upon the lithium electrodisolution and electrodeposition in (d) pristine Li metal electrodes and (e) sputter coated Li metal electrodes.

FIGURE 5

Evolution of the lithium intensity in the bulk and HSAL from the operando ^7Li NMR measurements during the lithium electrodeposition process at a current density of 0.5 mA/cm^2 , using 1 M LiTFSI in $\text{DME:DOL } 1:1$ (v/v) for 6.25 mAh/cm^2 . The ^7Li chemical shift for the Li bulk signal was at 246 ppm while the Li HSAL signal was at $266/269 \text{ ppm}$ (see Fig. S4).

HSAL) occurs earlier in case of the pristine Li metal electrodes. Even though the Zn@Li metal electrode shows presence of HSAL (as presented in Fig. 4b), less HSAL is formed, while the same amount of Li is electrodeposited compared to the pristine Li metal electrode. This may be an indication that the formation of HSAL for the Zn@Li electrodes occurs more homogeneously possibly due to a more effective transport of Li-ions, as also suggested by the morphological measurements in Fig. 4. In addition, these results further strengthen the role played by the LiZn intermetallic phase in both directing the lithium deposits and delaying the formation of HSAL, although only for a limited lithium amount transferred. However, the mechanical and electrochemical properties of the Li-intermetallic phase still need further improvement in order to completely eliminate the formation of HSAL as shown in Fig. 4c.

The evolution of the cell overvoltages as a function of current density for the 2-electrode symmetric cells assembled with pristine Li, Au@Li and Zn@Li metal electrodes are presented in Fig. 6. The variation of the current density was carried out to evaluate the effect of the lithiophilic layer sputtered on Li metal

electrodes on the overvoltage and cycling stability in such Li-symmetrical cells. The cells were cycled using the current densities of $0.1, 0.25, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0,$ and 4.0 mA/cm^2 for 25 cycles and limiting the total capacity transported to 0.113 mAh . In Fig. 6a, it was observed that the $\text{Li}||\text{Li}$ symmetrical cells perform inferior to both the $\text{Au@Li}||\text{Au@Li}$ and $\text{Zn@Li}||\text{Zn@Li}$ symmetrical cells. Especially, the former cells show higher overvoltages during the initial cycling at 0.1 mA/cm^2 and fluctuations after the C-rate test as compared to the latter, when the current density was switched back to 0.25 mA/cm^2 .

Often, the shape, and later the evolution, of the overvoltages during the lithium electrodeposition and electrodisolution reaction provides detailed information on the occurring processes at the Li metal electrodes. Bieker et al. [42] indicated that fracturing of the “native film” and SEI upon cycling usually results in a decrease of the overvoltage during the electrodeposition and electrodisolution process. The overvoltages of the Li-symmetric cells when cycled at $0.1, 2$ and 4 mA/cm^2 (Fig. 6b), show decreasing overvoltage values for the pristine Li metal electrodes when cycled at 0.1 mA/cm^2 . However, such behavior is not observed at higher current densities as the values are also similar (Fig. S5). Nevertheless, at 0.1 mA/cm^2 , the observed behavior is also in accordance with the possible fracturing of the “native film” and SEI during the electrodeposition process which results in the formation of fresh metallic Li. On the other side, both the $\text{Au@Li}||\text{Au@Li}$ and $\text{Zn@Li}||\text{Zn@Li}$ -symmetric cells did not show any changes in the overvoltages with increasing cycle number, indicating that the presence of the LiZn and $\text{Li}_{15}\text{-Au}_4$ intermetallic phases at the surface of the Li metal electrodes prevent such breakdown of the “native film” and the SEI. This is due to the fact, that the LiZn and $\text{Li}_{15}\text{-Au}_4$ intermetallic phases act already as a stable interphase for the lithium electrodeposition and electrodisolution process at the surface of the Li metal electrode. Due to the effective transport of Li-ions through the intermetallic interphase, the fracture and exposure of fresh metallic Li surface, which would result in a variation of the overvoltage, can be avoided. Therefore, when such Li-intermetallic phases are present at the interface to the electrolyte, a different diffusion coefficient for the Li-ions is provided and, thus, could control the formation of HSAL. A Li-ion diffusion coefficient for the

FIGURE 6

Evolution of the cell voltage of symmetrical cells assembled with Li, Au@Li , and Zn@Li electrodes (a) upon extended cycling at various current densities and (b) the 25 cycles with a current density of $0.1, 2$ and 4 mA/cm^2 . In all experiments, the lithium capacity for each electrodeposition and electrodisolution process was 0.113 mAh using 1 M LiTFSI in $\text{DME:DOL } 1:1$ (v/v) as electrolyte at 20°C .

LiZn-intermetallic phases of $4.8 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$ was reported in literature [53] and is almost two orders of magnitude higher than the Li-ion diffusion coefficient within the major “native film” constituents, such as Li_2CO_3 and Li_2O [54,55].

Besides Li-symmetric cells, the electrochemical behavior of the sputter coated Li metal electrodes with lithiophilic layers was compared with the pristine Li metal electrode in $\text{S}_8\|\text{Li}$ cells (Fig. 7). We remind that in such configuration, during the initial cycle, first the lithium electrodisolution process occurs (i.e. discharge process for the S_8 electrode) prior the lithium electrodeposition process (i.e. charge process for the S_8 electrode). Therefore, the improved overvoltage behavior, as discussed before, was expected to have a beneficial impact on the processes in such full-cells, as well. In these cells, also the potential of the negative electrode (i.e. Li metal electrode) was recorded using the auxiliary channels of the battery testing unit. Fig. 7a presents the potential profiles of the S_8 composite cathode during the initial two cycles at a 0.1C-rate using 1 M LiTFSI in DME:DOL 1:1 (v/v). There are neither substantial differences between the potential profiles inherent to the S_8 conversion to Li_2S via long chain and short chain lithium polysulfides observed between the various Li metal electrodes, nor the negative electrodes seem to have any influence on the potential profiles of the S_8 composite cathode or the Coulombic efficiency of such full-cells (the calculated Coulombic efficiencies during the first cycle were D/C: 102.6% for $\text{S}_8\|\text{Li}$; 99.6% for $\text{S}_8\|\text{Au@Li}$ and 99.9% for $\text{S}_8\|\text{Zn@Li}$). However, in Fig. 7b differences between the overpotentials of the various Li metal electrodes were observed. Fig. 7b shows the selected overvoltage profiles of the Li metal electrodes until the 10th cycle (larger insets) and upon cycling until the $\text{S}_8\|\text{Li}$ cells completed. In these plots, a rather significant change in the overpotentials for the electrodisolution process is observed with lower values for the coated Li metal electrodes with lithiophilic layers. The overall cycling performance of the $\text{S}_8\|\text{Li}$ cells, presented from the perspective of the overpotentials evolution of the Li metal electrodes, indicates improved performance (longer cycling stability) for the Li metal electrodes when Li-intermetallic phases (i.e. $\text{Li}_{15}\text{Au}_4$, LiZn) are present at the interface. In these Li metal electrodes, after 10 cycles with a C-rate of 0.1C, the overpotentials of the negative electrodes with Li-intermetallic phases were

$\approx 10 \text{ mV}$ (absolute value) compared to the overpotentials of the control Li metal electrodes (pristine Li metal electrodes) which amounted to 39 mV (absolute values). The overpotential values recorded during the lithium electrodisolution process (positive values) varied insignificantly from the overpotential values during the lithium electrodeposition process (negative values), therefore, the absolute value was reported. These results indicate that the sputter deposition method resulting in the formation of lithiophilic layers (Li-intermetallic) at the surface of the Li metal electrodes, can be used as a promising approach to fulfill the requirements of a highly performant artificial-SEI and to improve the performance of high energy LMBs through engineering of the Li metal electrodes.

Conclusions

Sputter coating of Li metal electrodes with Au and Zn lithiophilic layers results in the direct formation of the corresponding Li-intermetallic phases (i.e. $\text{Li}_{15}\text{Au}_4$ and LiZn). The presence of the Li intermetallic layer showed favorable properties towards the redirection of the lithium deposits and the suppression of HSAL (“lithium dendrite”) formation during the lithium electrodeposition and electrodisolution process. Although such Li-intermetallic layers can only prevent the formation of HSAL for lower amounts of transported charge, an overall improvement of the cycling stability with lower overvoltages and good rate capability could be obtained. Furthermore, in $\text{Cu}\|\text{Li}$ cells, higher Coulombic efficiencies were obtained when the Li-intermetallic phase was not completely delithiated, which was maintained even in $\text{S}_8\|\text{Li}$ cells. Moreover, the electrochemical performance of these Li metal electrodes clearly indicated lower overpotentials for the Li-intermetallic phase coated Li metal electrodes during the discharge (lithium electrodisolution) and charge (lithium electrodeposition) process within $\text{S}_8\|\text{Li}$ cells. The results presented here, indicate that a sputter deposition of Li metal electrodes with lithiophilic Au and Zn forming Li-intermetallic phases provides a facile technique to improve the performance of Li metal electrodes in order to fulfill the requirements of a highly performant artificial-SEI-on-Li for future high energy LMBs.

FIGURE 7

Potential profiles of (a) S_8 composite electrode showing the first 2 cycles at 0.1C and (b) the Li metal electrodes (pristine, Au@Li, Zn@Li) during cycling of the $\text{S}_8\|\text{Li}$ cells in 1 M LiTFSI in DME:DOL 1:1 (v/v) as electrolyte and a 3-electrode configuration with Li as reference electrode.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Marian Cristian Stan: Writing - original draft, Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Data curation, Supervision, Writing - review & editing, Project administration. **Jens Becking:** Data curation, Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing - review & editing. **Aleksei Kolesnikov:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation, Writing - review & editing. **Björn Wankmiller:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation, Validation, Writing - review & editing. **Joop Enno Frerichs:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation, Validation, Writing - review & editing. **Michael Ryan Hansen:** Supervision, Writing - review & editing. **Peter Bieker:** Funding acquisition, Project administration, Writing - review & editing. **Martin Kolek:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing - review & editing. **Martin Winter:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge financial support from the European Commission through the Horizon 2020 framework program for research and innovation within the HELIS project under Grant Agreement No. 666221 and from the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) for the financial support within the project BCT-Battery Cell Technology (03XP0109I).

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mattod.2020.04.002>.

References

- [1] M. Winter, B. Barnett, K. Xu, *Chem. Rev.* 118 (23) (2018) 11433–11456.
- [2] T. Placke et al., *J. Solid State Electrochem.* 21 (7) (2017) 1939–1964.
- [3] R. Schmuck et al., *Nat. Energy* 3 (4) (2018) 267–278.
- [4] J. Betz et al., *Adv. Energy Mater.* 9 (21) (2019) 1900574.
- [5] W. Xu et al., *Energy Environ. Sci.* 7 (2) (2014) 513–537.
- [6] X.-B. Cheng et al., *Chem. Rev.* 117 (15) (2017) 10403–10473.
- [7] W. Li et al., *ACS Nano* 11 (6) (2017) 5853–5863.
- [8] L.E. Marbella et al., *Chem. Mater.* 31 (8) (2019) 2762–2769.
- [9] N. Delaporte, Y. Wang, K. Zaghbi, *Front. Mater.* 6 (2019) 267.
- [10] X. Zeng et al., *Adv. Energy Mater.* 9 (27) (2019) 1900161.
- [11] J. Ko, Y.S. Yoon, *Ceram. Int.* 45 (1) (2019) 30–49.
- [12] H. Kim et al., *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 42 (2013) 9011–9034.
- [13] J. Heine et al., *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 162 (6) (2015) A1094–A1101.
- [14] H. Kuwata et al., *Electrochemistry* 84 (11) (2016) 854–860.
- [15] X. Liang et al., *J. Power Sources* 196 (22) (2011) 9839–9843.
- [16] R. Miao et al., *J. Power Sources* 271 (2014) 291–297.
- [17] J. Guo et al., *Electrochem. Commun.* 51 (2015) 59–63.
- [18] A. Mauger et al., *Mater. Sci. Eng.: R Rep.* 134 (2018) 1–21.
- [19] G. Zheng et al., *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 9 (8) (2014) 618–623.
- [20] E. Peled, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 126 (12) (1979) 2047–2051.
- [21] M. Winter, J.O. Besenhard, Lithiated carbons, in: *Handbook of Battery Materials*, 1998, pp. 383–418.
- [22] M. Winter, *Z. Phys. Chem.* 223 (2009) 1395.
- [23] E. Peled, S. Menkin, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 164 (7) (2017) A1703–A1719.
- [24] F.-S. Li et al., *Adv. Mater.* 27 (1) (2015) 130–137.
- [25] C. Yan et al., *J. Power Sources* 327 (2016) 212–220.
- [26] H. Lee et al., *J. Power Sources* 284 (2015) 103–108.
- [27] M. Wu et al., *Electrochim. Acta* 103 (2013) 199–205.
- [28] M.-H. Ryou et al., *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 25 (6) (2015) 834–841.
- [29] J. Becking et al., *Interfaces* 4 (16) (2017) 1700166.
- [30] J. Park et al., *Interfaces* 3 (11) (2016) 1600140.
- [31] P. Schmitz et al., *PCCP* 19 (29) (2017) 19178–19187.
- [32] X.X. Zeng et al., *Mater. Today Nano* 8 (2019) 100057.
- [33] Y.J. Zhang et al., *J. Power Sources* 266 (2014) 43–50.
- [34] Q. Chen et al., *J. Mater. Chem. A* 7 (19) (2019) 11683–11689.
- [35] R. Song et al., *J. Mater. Chem. A* 7 (30) (2019) 18126–18134.
- [36] M. Genovese et al., *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 165 (13) (2018) A3000–A3013.
- [37] Q. Tang et al., *Ionics* 25 (6) (2019) 2525–2533.
- [38] G. He et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* (2019).
- [39] A. Paoletta et al., *J. Power Sources* 427 (2019) 201–206.
- [40] Y. Xu et al., *Adv. Mater.* 31 (29) (2019) 1901662.
- [41] X. Wang et al., *J. Mater. Chem. A* 7 (32) (2019) 19104–19111.
- [42] G. Bieker, M. Winter, P. Bieker, *PCCP* 17 (14) (2015) 8670–8679.
- [43] R. Nölle et al., *Mater. Today* 32 (2020) 131–146.
- [44] V. Küpers et al., *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 21 (2019) 26084–26094.
- [45] D. Massiot et al., *Magn. Reson. Chem.* 40 (1) (2002) 70–76.
- [46] R. Bhattacharyya et al., *Nat. Mater.* 9 (6) (2010) 504–510.
- [47] J.O. Besenhard, J. Yang, M. Winter, *J. Power Sources* 68 (1) (1997) 87–90.
- [48] M. Winter et al., *Adv. Mater.* 10 (10) (1998) 725–763.
- [49] M. Wachtler, J.O. Besenhard, M. Winter, *J. Power Sources* 94 (2) (2001) 189–193.
- [50] M. Winter et al., Lithium storage alloys as anode materials in lithium ion batteries, in: L. Breveglieri (Ed.), *Progress in Batteries and Battery Materials*, 1998, pp. 208–214.
- [51] K. Yan et al., *Energy* 1 (3) (2016) 16010.
- [52] A. Varzi et al., *Adv. Energy Mater.* 8 (1) (2018) 1701706.
- [53] J.L. Gole, Z. Shi, M. Liu, *Philos. Mag. B* 81 (2) (2001) 119–131.
- [54] F.A. Soto et al., *Chem. Mater.* 30 (10) (2018) 3315–3322.
- [55] L. Benitez, J.M. Seminario, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 164 (11) (2017) E3159–E3170.